

Data Librarianship in 21st Century: Issues and Challenges

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Abstract

The nature of scientific research in the twenty-first century is more collaborative and data intensive (NSFP 2010). ICTs have made it possible to assess, understand, and arrive at novel conclusions by incorporating rigorous computation, simulation, and modelling. Massive amounts of born-digital and digitised data are being created at a rapid rate in a wide range of ways. Digital data are not only the results of study, but also the sources of new theories that enable fresh scientific understanding and spur innovation (NSFP 2008). Due to this, a lot of data has been generated that has to be reused and shared with others for further analysis and interpretation. UNESCO recognized that valuable progress could be stimulated in both developed and developing countries by assuring that compilations of reliable data would be readily available to all scientists, researchers, academicians, engineers and policymakers. A good number of initiatives have been taken worldwide by many institutions (KIIT-Germany, Purdue-USA, and University of Cambridge etc.), funded agencies (NSF, NIH, NEH, and UNESCO etc), publishers (Nature, PLOS ONE, Lancet, Springer, and Elsevier etc), governments (India, Canada, Germany, UK, USA etc), learned bodies and other stakeholders to develop a sustainable ecosystem for research data sharing and re-use for the better science. Industries, academic and research institutions in India and abroad have started to hiring “data librarian” (sometimes data curator, data manager, databrarian, research data librarian, data service librarian, repository manager, etc.) to manage, archive and share of reproducible large quantitative research data. Generally, scientists are generating data by pursuing research but less interested about data preservation and share. So the information professionals can play the role efficiently and satisfy the social need. A few LIS schools in Europe have been conducting short term training courses on Research Data Management (RDM) and Data Science to fill the employers need, unfortunately, none of the Indian LIS schools yet not have adopted any data management component in their curriculum except DRTC. In this context

there is a need to identify the core competencies of information professionals required in order to manage research data for long-term preservation, dissemination, and advocacy in the digital environment. It also investigates, what are the issues faced by the data librarians and stack holders to provide research data services (RDS) to the scientific community. By understanding what employers seek in data librarians, LIS curriculum developers can better implement courses and pedagogy that will help meet employer needs as well as developing qualified candidates for these new job titles in academic and research libraries.

Keywords: *Research Data Management; RDM; Big Data; Data Librarian; LIS Curriculum*

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